

Interview Günter P. Wagner

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Q: How would you define yourself as a researcher?

R: I think we all define biography, and what we end up being is a mixture of things that we went through. I still define myself as a lab chemist, my earliest training was in biochemical engineering, which led me to study biology later. I found that chemistry is a beautiful science but in a way intellectually closed because it covers a field that is already defined by the 92 naturally occurring chemical elements and all the combinations that are possible among them, and what fascinated me about biology is that, in contrast, it deals with a process, namely evolution, that is inherently creative and new things and entities arise in evolution. That is sort of the motivating idea that led me from being a physical scientist into a biologist: I wanted to know what it is about life and evolution that enables this open-ended creativity. So I have to define myself as an evolutionary biologist motivated by the contrast between life and inorganic nature.

Q: It seems like you had two parallel lives in functional and evolutionary biology, publishing in both. How would you describe the state of both fields at that time?

R: I think the early 1980s was a time with a lot of dissatisfaction with the reductionist bias of the Evolutionary Synthesis, which was becoming acute in some corners of biology. But it didn't reach a level where there was an alternative research paradigm that actually could support research leading away from the way evolutionary biology was done in the mid-20th century. It's also interesting that the beginning of devo-evo as a field is identified with the discovery and widespread occurrence of homeobox genes and other conserved regulatory genes [...] But the conference that is often seen as the beginning of the field as a movement, as a community, the 1981 Dahlem Conference on Development and Evolution, which is at least half a decade before that. So it's clear that the discovery of the molecular similarities that then helped forge an experimental, empirical paradigm, was meeting a field that was ready to move in that direction. The theme was already clear.

Reading Alan Love's summary of the 1981 Dahlem Conference I rediscovered a lot of topics that I thought I had encountered later. They were already there and discussed. One of them was cell type evolution. My own more active interest in going in that direction [Arendt et al. 2016] came from hearing Detlev Arendt's talk at the phylogenetic symposium around 2005, while the idea that we want to understand (the origin and diversification of cell types) is already a topic that was articulated during

that conference, but I completely forgot about it. As a list of agendas, the field already existed by the end of the 1970s and early 2000s, but required technical advances that allowed them to do something about it.

Q: Do you think the idea of evolvability was also somehow present in the origin of evolutionary biology?

R: Very often, the topics arrive early, but the question is whether they precipitate sustained research effort or not. Clearly, the problem of evolvability was one that Darwin also discussed, but I think that most people in classical evolutionary biology would have said that with what Darwin said everything was already settled, more or less. There's Fisher's geometric model of adaptation, which was also an insular contribution and didn't have a lot of follow-up. The way I see it, evolvability becomes a concept with more prospects of driving a research agenda through the emergence of evolutionary approaches in computer science and also in engineering. One of the earliest pioneers there that I'm aware of is Ingo Rechenberg, a German aircraft engineer who developed an approach to solving complex optimization problems that are based on random changes and measuring their effects. They quickly discovered that they had to finetune the variation in their device in a way that allows the optimization of a complex device. In his case, it was mostly flow-dynamical devices, and they are complicated because airflow and fluid flow are highly nonlinear phenomena, so it's not easy to predict which changes to an airplane improve a certain performance function. So the mathematical models were intrinsically less successful in improving these things, and it turned out that unexpected solutions could be found if you used random changes, if the random changes are tuned to the problem at hand. This means that the engineering approach to using evolutionary methods had to include a feedback loop that optimizes the evolvability of that device. So functional optimization and evolvability were two things that had to happen at the same time.

The intuition, of course, is that organisms are not less complex than these systems. So, by implication, it has to be true for organisms as well. Then, the independent development of evolutionary genetic programming by Holland and others in the US more or less all came to the same conclusion, namely that you can successfully use random change as a way to improve things if and only if the variational process is tuned appropriately to solve these problems. So evolvability is not a trivial state of any replicating and varying system but needs to be built into the system in order to be possible.

And this relates to your previous question: often it's not so much about misunderstandings but about under what conditions a type of question actually precipitates a more sustained effort in research. What these conditions are I don't know; that's probably something you guys have to figure out. It's generally not appropriate to say that only because a problem was brought up and briefly discussed a long time ago, it was already there as a research program. For me, what ultimately counts is whether that thinking leads to more research and insights.

Q: What do you consider as your first work on evolvability?

R: I think the first one, which is more or less a summary of the core results of my dissertation, is a 1981 paper on “feedback selection” [Wagner 1981]. The question there was whether genes whose only effect is to increase “evolvability” (as we’d say today) could be selected by Darwinian selection. Given it was published in 1981, admittedly in an obscure place and by an obscure person, that might explain why the basic insight hasn’t penetrated the field more broadly. And the insight is the fact that there’s nothing inherently obscure in assuming that natural selection, even by competition among individuals, can increase the frequency of genetic variants that positively influence evolvability [...]

R: In [Wagner 1981] I convinced myself that the evolution of evolvability by natural selection is possible, or at least that it can be accommodated in a normal population genetics framework, without species or group selection necessarily. But then there were two follow-up questions. The first one was about recombination, which wasn’t present in that paper. Many people, like Lynch, complain that this only works if there’s a strict linkage between genes that do the adapting and the ones that are influencing evolvability. That was the work on dominance modifiers that was followed up on by Reinhard Bürger mostly. The other one was that, if natural selection can evolve high evolvability, then what kind of properties would be expected to be enhanced by this type of selection? The [Wagner 1984] paper was taking the mathematical models that Rechenberg used to model his engineering devices, and applying them in a quantitative genetics context in order to see in what way his conclusions are also applicable in the population and quantitative genetics framework. His approach was dictated by the way he does his experiments: he takes a machine, changes one parameter or a number of them randomly, then tests it, and if it's better he keeps it whereas if not he changes it again. It was a one-step type of process, not a population one. But I wanted to see in what way the same needs for evolvability tuning are necessary if we consider the populational process rather than a single-step optimization one.

That was the motivation for that paper, and there’s a more extensive one in 1988 [1988a] in the *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*. There’s a series of them actually, and all of them developed the infrastructure in terms of technical results to fill in whether evolvability can evolve and how.

The interesting thing is that, at some point, particularly in the 1990s we ran into a brick wall. I understood what kind of variation you would expect to be good for evolvability; we had the other element which is that selection can improve evolvability under certain conditions; and we wanted to put it all together, like evolved modularity or evolved correlations and so on. That turned out to be unexpectedly difficult. And the reason why I couldn’t get my head around it in a satisfyingly broad way, was that we did not understand the consequences of epistasis well enough in order to get an idea of what was going on. And I think that a lot of the results that Thomas then did when we collaborated on modeling epistasis explain why it’s so difficult to evolve more complex models in a direction you

would intuitively expect them to evolve. I think that is still an open question: how that works and in what way selection for evolvability plays a role in it [...]

It's an experience that replicates itself also in the context of canalization, which is sort of a complement to evolvability, or like a negative evolution of evolvability. I had a 1997 paper in *Evolution* [Wagner 1997] about a genetic theory of canalization when originally I thought I was ready to model the evolution of evolvability. I thought of doing first the simplest thing, which is modeling one character under stabilizing selection. That was supposed to be sort of the first footnote of a big paper on the evolution of evolvability, but it turned out to become a whole cottage industry of really complex and difficult questions. I think the biggest discovery along those lines is that many things that seem intuitively obvious are in reality not. If you seriously try to understand them, model them mathematically, or measure them in an experiment or in nature, it's more like a continuous discovery of complexity than of simple answers. In a way, you have a narrative or a feeling where you expect to already know what the answer will be because it seems obvious, but I think it's still not trivial.

Q: You worked very early on neglected aspects in population genetics such as epistasis, canalization, or pleiotropy. How were those papers received by the community of population geneticists?

R: Well, I think it was a heterogeneous response. A coherent field is usually defined both by methods and agreement upon interesting and legitimate questions. I was deliberately looking for areas where this approach was falling short, and therefore there was no interest in it. But it was variable. One little anecdote is that when we were publishing [Wagner and Altenberg 1996], I had a visit by Alexey Kondrashov, and I told him what I was doing. I said "We're doing this, but don't take it too seriously", and his response was "Yes! This is exactly what we need". So it really depends on what scientific culture people are coming from. I think that the core population genetics community was on the one hand intrigued but at the same time somewhat disturbed by what we were doing. I wouldn't say that, for example, my work on canalization wasn't well received. I got invited and, because it was written in an as rigorous population genetics theoretical way as possible, it was respected. It didn't generate a lot of interest in it though. So it's mixed: I cannot complain because people respected me to some degree as a theoretical population geneticist, but the program that drove my interest was appreciated by a rather small community, and mostly people coming from other cultures. So not only nature is complex, but also the history of the reception of research efforts is complex depending on where the people come from and where they want to go.

Q: Who else would you say that at that time contributed to building this bridge in the field of population genetics?

R: Greg Gibson was interested in canalization, and mostly people who came from the Cheverud lab. It was a small group. In connection to this, something that shows the connection with Cheverud is that the reason why I got into evolvability from a population genetics view was Riedl's proposal that a structured body plan, with its inherent constraints, can be understood as an answer to the problem of evolvability. A complex system with many variables to optimize has a serious problem of evolvability or optimizability. There were also independent developments in optimization theory within engineering, such as the "curse of dimensionality" idea, which is a concept that plays a big role in computer science and engineering. Riedl thought that if that was the case, that is, if we do have complex body plans structured in a way where some things are correlated and others aren't, maybe that could be an answer to the problem of dimensionality. That would basically mean taking all the complexity and packaging it appropriately with respect to the function of the parts. Then you have different ways of doing that, meaning different body plans explaining macroevolutionary diversity and so on. That was the broad ingenious idea. I was deputized, as his student, to try to figure out how much of that can actually work. Thus the evolution of evolvability problem.

One has to know that one of the few American evolutionary biologists who actually read Riedl was Jim Cheverud, and that motivated some of his early work. So there's actually a lot of not very visible intellectual influence from Riedl to motivate ways of going beyond the standard paradigm of population genetics-based evolutionary biology. The core deficit of that synthetic theory was the complete elimination of theoretical inputs from the organism; it screened off everything that had to do with the actual lives of organisms and collapsed that into a single parameter of fitness on the one hand. On the other hand, it left it open at a lower level of the genome; so it was genome and fitness, and that was all. So a lot of the work that Jim, others, and myself were trying was to build a conceptual infrastructure where, based on the unquestionable achievements of the evolutionary synthesis and population genetics, we could build into this void a theoretical framework to help us articulate issues that have to do with the structure and evolution of the organism itself.

Q: In those works, you refer to "evolutionary systems biology", defined as a way to understand how mechanisms in population genetics work under the boundary conditions of the organism (Wagner 1989c). The term is now used differently. Was it established at that time?

R: No, it had a different meaning but it's overlapping, of course. You cannot innovate in science by expecting to do things that have a broad basis at the time. It was a small group of people that were either connected to or inspired by Riedl's ideas. Riedl's main theoretical contribution, his book *Order in living organisms*, had a subtitle: "a system theory of evolution" [Riedl 1978]. This meant essentially that the interdependence of the parts of the body influence the dynamics of evolution. That was reformulated in my context, population genetics.

Q: Would you say that what you named evolutionary systems biology at the time gave rise to developmental evolution?

R: I think devo-evo has deep roots, all the way back into the morphological and embryological traditions of the 19th century and early 20th century, and also other sources of dissatisfaction with the population genetic way of thinking about evolution. I think it all came together, this strand of thinking coming from Riedl and associates was one contributing factor. Gerd Müller is a Riedl's student, I am one, and we're both recognized in the devo-evo field, but of course, I wouldn't claim that everything came from that corner. It would be silly and ahistorical.

Q: While evo-devo has tended to focus on the problem of form, you have always considered the role of function in your work. Where does that come from?

R: It's rooted in the idea that evolvability needs to solve the problem of the curse of dimensionality, which is the problem of improving things by natural selection. They have to evolve and be able to adjust to changes in the biotic and abiotic environment and so on. So the whole idea of where evolvability plays a theoretical role in evolutionary biology, from where I'm coming from, always included the idea that it's about the possibility of adaptation.

In that context, innovation is another chapter, but of course, we always have to think about organisms as those that need to be able to survive and reproduce. You cannot separate those things, even though I'm certainly identified in some way with a sort of structuralist approach to evolution. But I cannot divorce myself from the fact that function (survival and reproduction) is the core of being alive.

Q: You've always been concerned with the importance of having adequate definitions of concepts, as well as means to measure them (Houle et al. 2011)

R: I think that the train of thought that led in that direction was that if evolvability changes, that means that the organism, or the genome, has to change its variational properties, meaning that the same DNA change has different phenotypic consequences (e.g., being more robust, stronger, etc.). That means that the role that changes of genes can play depends on other genes in the same genome, that is, they are context-dependent. That is, by definition, epistasis. In the classical population genetics theory, epistasis was dismissed as unimportant because in a first approximation, it doesn't influence the selection response, even if Thomas has proven that that's not literally true. There's a joke about that: the question is why Fisher called it epistasis, it's derived from the Greek word ἐπίστασις (epístasis), which means "the thing that stands on top=scum". So basically he gave it a dirty name and equally dismissed it. In classical population genetics theory, it's largely something to average over, because the main concern was the changing gene frequency or the change in the mean of a character under

natural selection, and there the influence of epistasis is small. And if you think that those two types of evolutionary change are the only ones worth studying, epistasis doesn't play a role.

However, if you think that variational properties of organisms change in evolution, you want to know how they do it, and thus there has to be fundamentally a question of how epistatic effects and other forms of context-dependency contribute to and are involved in evolutionary change at the population genetic level.

The reason that then leads to questions of measurement is that the classical way of taking epistasis into account is theoretically ungrounded. It's a deviation from additivity, but there's no theoretical justification for why it is additivity. Why not multiplicativity? Why not other forms of combining effects? That led me to the question of what scale types are and how we define quantitative concepts. How to properly define epistasis is the problem of how to define a quantitative concept, which is measurement theory. Those were the inferential steps that led me there. We had to understand how measurement theory and the invention of new quantitative properties work in order to properly develop the notion and the theory of epistasis. And, as it turns out, in most cases it's not additivity per se but multiplicativity, because of the scale type. Now you can measure epistasis appropriately so that it interacts with the population genetics theory. That was the logical connection with the general concern with the evolution of evolvability and systems of traits.

Q: Are these measures of common use now in population genetics?

R: [...] I think the younger generation will be more careful in that respect, or at least that's the hope, but I don't know. I can just throw out things and hope they survive and get taken up. I think I have a very strong logical-mathematical reason for my position. If that's historically stable then it will influence the field in the long run. If it's not, then something else has to come along.

Q: How do you think your work on epistasis (e.g. [Hermisson et al. 2003](#), [Hansen et al. 2006](#)) has challenged the assumptions of classical additive models?

Those papers are cited more frequently than I was afraid they would. They are hard to read, but on the other hand, the frustration is that some of the most visible exponents of the field rejected them at the time it came out, and then reinvented it in their own work without attribution. I find the whole field of theoretical population genetics a little bit frustrating as a community because it seems to be always dismissing new ideas but then reinventing them without making references. Other parts of biology [e.g. reproductive biology] are more attentive to what I'm saying.

[...] This whole field seems so insular. The way I see younger people coming into the field there's a lot of reinvention and very little actually studying the papers that are older than three years or so. So you find a lot of reinventing of it, which is fine. Multiple people coming to the same conclusion means it's

probably objectively true, and that should be OK. You never ask an author about his or her actual impact on the field because, first of all, they cannot know it. Second, it affects the vanity of the person.

Q: But you say the additive model is valid as an approximation in certain scenarios. What is the scope of this approximation?

R: The main objective was to understand changes in the mean value of a character, such as body size. If you want to predict short-term changes in mean value, some form of additive variation is what is the most relevant. For those reasons the additive effect plays a role and is not an assumption: it is part of genetic variation that can be approximated with a linear regression. That's not just a mathematical artifact, because it turns out that this part that can be predicted as a linear regression is the thing that predicts most actual little changes of the mean. That's what additive variance means. It doesn't mean that genes themselves are additive or linear at the physiological level ... This is a matter of degree, and the degree of context-insensitivity is what we call additive effects. This is the entirely appropriate way of looking at things even if the main variable of your interest is changes in mean value in evolution, which is a legitimate thing to ask.

The things that I'm interested in, and now actually a broader field that overlaps with evolutionary systems biology, like robustness, canalization, or evolvability, are all phenomena that are linked to variational properties of the organism. And those are highly influenced by gene interactions, epistasis, and so on. There are different ways to try to get a handle on it, and I think there are two main ones. The first one is the one Thomas and I have worked on in terms of quantitative characters in the tradition of quantitative genetics taking into account genotypes and so on. Another way of doing it is motivated by the molecular evolution literature, where you don't talk about quantitative measures of some attribute of an organism, but you look into the combinatorial space of DNA or amino acid sequences. There you use different mathematical tools. From there come the ideas about neutral networks in Peter Schuster's school, Walter Fontana's, and a little bit more independently, Andreas Wagner's. These ideas about neutral networks and neutral domains capture epistasis, or context-dependency, in a geometrical way of thinking, where the neighbourhood relationships of these neutral networks influence the probability of mutations changing the phenotype. It's an alternative mathematical approach to capture the fact of context-dependency. These fields now are pretty broadly represented in the work of Andreas, who was my student, and I think it's not a coincidence that he got interested in robustness and variational properties, as well as evolvability. I think it's now a field where the agenda is about variational properties such as robustness and evolvability, and a number of different mathematical approaches try to get a handle on what aspects of GPF maps influence these variational properties.

Q: Why did these two approaches stay apart?

R: We've known for a long time that a GP map that is highly nonlinear can have a lot of additive variance if the gene frequencies of the interacting genes are very different. If some of the alleles have low frequency or are fixed, interacting genes where one gene is not varying have an additive effect. So you can have a highly nonlinear developmental or physiological system, and depending on the population genetics structure of the population, you can have a lot of additive genetic variance or less. Jim Cheverud has shown this clearly [Cheverud & Routman 1995], and other people too: there are at least 4 to 6 independent derivations of this effect. Everyone who seriously is in the field should know about this argument that there being little epistatic variance measured in natural populations doesn't tell us anything about how nonlinear or context-dependent the function of genes is. That shouldn't even be a point of discussion. But there're still people who infer that everything is additive because they found low epistatic variance, and that's bullshit. It's unbelievable intellectual inertia that I just cannot explain. Someone who's supposed to be smart enough to be a professor insists on a position when it's plainly obvious that it's just bullshit. I don't understand that psychologically.

Q: But there's also the opposite attitude from computational approaches ignoring population genetics principles...

R: It's just hard. You try to make things easier by redefining your problem in a way that screens out things that are too hard to work on, or that people are not motivated enough to make the effort to include. I think it's a matter of complexity reduction that everyone in their life is doing. And there's also a fragmentation coming from the fact that the body of knowledge is so vast and it's just not easy. It's not just isolation by distance. The field of population genetics is too heterogeneous and broad, and it cannot be taught in any comprehensive way. And you don't want to make your life harder than it has to be to be successful. I think all of this adds to the heterogeneity and lack of communication that we see. I'm not blameless in that respect: I ignore a lot of bodies of knowledge that I should know about simply because I can't stand learning something in addition to what I already have to know. Unless we come to a point in the development of the field where there are a lot of unifying principles that make it easy to communicate and travel between different parts of the field. That would be like having more highways so that it's easier to travel. I wouldn't be optimistic about the future unless such ways of having conceptual continuity are reached.

Q: Do the differences in kind of phenotypes play a role as well in communication?

R: Yes, but I think that's a matter of time. The neutral networks approach was originally done in RNA molecules and their secondary structure folding. But the work that Andreas Wagner and Joshua Payne are doing is precisely trying to apply these ideas to non-molecules, like genetic networks. So I see that these ideas are strong enough to inspire work that pushes the boundaries of the original field of application. I think these fields can eventually fuse together. For example, Joshua is working on quantitative phenotypes coarse-grained into discrete ones, and he also discretizes the genotype that he

takes into account. This is very close to a point where he and others would actually have to do quantitative genetics. So I think that is also a matter of how the field can grow and how much effort is required to grow the field outwards to new fields of application.

Q: The mutational covariance matrix is a key tool for modeling variational properties in quantitative genetics.

R: But it's hard to measure. Although some people are more willing to do that in systems where that's easier to measure than in fruit flies. For instance, Mark Siegal is properly measuring mutational variance and covariance matrices in yeast populations, and he comes to really interesting conclusions. Implicitly, many people use G-Matrices as a token, or as an approximation of the mutational effect matrix, with all the caveats that that implies.

It's becoming easier. Nowadays we can measure gene expression of tens of thousands of genes simultaneously. I think it's a matter of technology, whether you can do something with it rather than deep conceptual difficulty.

Q: You often cite [Lande 1980](#) as the introduction of the M-Matrix. How was it introduced and how did it impact the field of quantitative genetics?

R: The M-Matrix is actually a dispositional property in quantitative genetics, which is very weird, and that's the interesting thing. The population genetics "ideology" made this main point about the fundamental nature of variation as the lowest level of ontological reality for evolutionary biology. It was a field that already had the seed of its own destruction. But that is often the case: turning science into ideology only works by simplifying things and not seeing things that go beyond that framework [...] You are doing it yourself even if you don't want to.

Q: Do you agree with [Thomas Hansen](#) that the maintenance of variation is also an important part of evolvability, an issue you have worked on as well ([Wagner 1996](#))?

R: Yes and no. The actual amount of genetic variation in a population is such an ephemeral thing that can change very quickly, such as because of migration. The reason I worked on the mutation-selection balance was because that's how a variational property such as the mutational variance and the mutation rate influences the mean fitness of the population. In order to understand how changes in the variational property itself influence mean fitness or can drive selection I have to know how much variation is maintained. So it was all in the service of understanding how selection can act on variational properties that I needed to have an opinion on that. That happened to be at the time highly controversial. The Lande-Turelli controversy also happened in the 1980s and 1990s. Someone working in the field at the time couldn't avoid having an opinion about that.

Q: You've worked on the notions of developmental and functional constraints (Wagner 1988a,b). How do you think constraints and evolvability relate?

R: Constraints are the complement of evolvability. That's under certain circumstances, following the line of thinking of Riedl and others who say that you need to constrain some dimensions of possible directions in order to improve your chances of being evolvable in the remaining directions of phenotype variability. The condensed argument of Riedl always was that you want to minimize the production of unconditionally deleterious variants to maximize the relative frequency of potentially adaptive variation. To allow variation that affects the center of the circulatory system or the functioning of the brain leaves very little room for variation that is potentially adaptive, so you want to buffer those things for which screwing around is unconditionally bad, and increase the variability of those things that are not unconditionally bad and therefore potentially adaptive. In that way, in the way I was brought up intellectually, evolvability and constraints were always the two sides of the same coin. That goes back to Riedl (1975). In a way, the discussion about constraints as it came up in early devo-evo always struck us as short-sighted, because it's not just that things cannot happen, but also things that we just don't want to happen or wouldn't be a good idea that they happened too frequently. They happen anyway, because we all die, but...

Q: You deepen into those ideas in your work with Kurt Schwenk (Wagner and Schwenk 2000; Schwenk and Wagner 2001; Schwenk and Wagner 2003), where you distinguish between functional and developmental constraints.

R: It's actually even more complex than Kurt Schwenk had thought of, because of the perspective pushed by Fritson Galis. She pointed out that many of the evolutionarily constrained characters might be due to unconditionally deleterious pleiotropic effects of mutations. For example, if you change the number of cervical vertebrae, you have a very strong correlation with childhood cancer. In a way, that's a mixed boundary between functional and developmental constraints, one that is a bit fussy, because even developmental constraints are in a way related to deleterious functional consequences. I told her that I think the actual point here is the fact that, developmentally, variation in one character and cancer incidence is highly correlated, and that's a variational, developmental constraint. This developmental constraint, then, is linked to unconditionally deleterious effects, which makes anything that's correlated with this effect evolutionarily constrained, because it would need a very high positive fitness effect to overcome the negative effect.

As always, I think categories are good to get started, to sort things out. But it may work out in a way that we need to have models, rather than categories, to accommodate different aspects of these concepts. At some point, concepts as categories can be useful to structure the field, but eventually, we might want to give them up and replace them with the idea that we have constraints and functional necessities interacting in interesting ways.

Q: This idea of pleiotropic effects is also very present in discussions on the paradox of stasis.

R: Canalization and constraints also have a paradoxical consequence that I think hasn't been fully understood. If you have something that is very robust and is constrained in the production of phenotypic variation, that means that any relevant genetic variation should accumulate as cryptic variation and become visible under certain circumstances. So there's a dialectic between robustness and evolvability that's overlooked in a lot of these discussions.

Q: You've been critical of explaining these dynamics in terms of molecular regulators of evolvability, such as Hsp-90 (Wagner et al. 1999).

R: This is actually what Mark Siegal with two examples in yeast has shown, that if you introduce a mutation of a heat shock protein, a deletion or whatever, that reveals genetic variation, and you then measure the mutational variance of the same trait with and without Hsp-90 or whatever, it's exactly the same. It actually is not decanalization, if you define canalization as the average effect of mutations on the trait. The whole school of thinking going back to Waddington that says that these major effect mutations that increase the variation are an indication of decanalization is totally flawed. [...] This only became clear when people started to mathematically model robustness and gene-environment interaction. Joachim Hermsisson did this in my lab [Hermsisson & Wagner 2004]. He showed that it was not necessary. Mark Siegal even empirically showed that it just doesn't change at all, and it's exactly the same mutational variance up to the level of accuracy of measurement [Richardson et al 2013]. Aviv Bergman found similar results with his gene regulatory networks models [Bergman & Siegal 2003]. I think that's one of the major steps forward in our understanding of variational properties: that a release of cryptic variation and canalization and robustness are completely different things and can exist in completely orthogonal directions.

Q: But then what's the relation between canalization and evolvability?

R: I think it's still the case that V_m determines the input of genetic variation that selection and drift can act on. So anything that can change V_m influences evolvability. But we don't understand how V_m can be changed, because the empirical examples turned out to be wrong. We don't have an answer yet, in part because we don't have the V_m , of homologous characters, in different species or populations, measured in different backgrounds. It's not trivial to measure V_m , because you have to do mutation-accumulation, which is hard and labor intensive. Unless we have ways of measuring V_m in different species, like David is doing with fly wings, we won't even know whether these variational properties are changing in evolution. Only when we have that we can ask why and in what way. So I think we are really not in the position to have a good empirical foundation for that field. It's obvious where to go, but there's a lot of work that will take generations because it's not a big field.

Q: Before Amundson's (2005) book was published, you used his notion of explanatory force to argue that devo-evo and population genetics offer complementary rather than exclusive explanations (Wagner 2000b). When it comes to evolvability, how do you see this division of labor?

R: We don't know what, whether, or how selection shapes variational properties that determine evolvability.

Each fortunate research program is the art of the possible, multiplied by the importance of the question. As a matter of principle, it should be self-evident that we need population genetics because evolution is a population phenomenon. But populations consist of organisms, and organisms have their problems to solve, and structure, and bring their own constraints and opportunities with them. In terms of the actual research programs, I think we will always see compartmentalization because you have to answer specific questions with specific results, and sometimes you need the one or the other perspective and sometimes you don't. Even though I'm theoretically sympathetic to integration, and I am, or was, a part of the population genetics community, my current work on the evolution of cell types and pregnancy has very little use for this population genetics perspective. You can divide your questions into how and why questions. But you can also use "how" questions in a transformational sense, for explaining the origin or transformation of characters. They are questions about "how" the cells did something and in what way they are different, say, in an opossum and a eutherian, or how it is possible that you can have a sustained wound in the uterus without inflammation that would destroy the fetus. There are many mechanistic questions even in an evolutionary transformation series that you want to understand in addition to the why-questions about natural selection. I think that conceptual continuity needs to be maintained on a sort of meta-biological level, and I wouldn't even encourage anyone to try to integrate it acutely into their research program. I think there are just too many variables, too many balls in the air to handle, in order to get any results that are respectable enough to be published.

Complexity reduction is the art of everything. All the research programs have to reduce the complexity of the question that they're asking. I think integration needs to be assessed at a meta-biology level. You have concrete biologies for each sub-field, but then you need a meta-biology theory that connects them and should be open to the contributions of other fields, some more population-oriented, others more mechanistic. That's different from what the structure of each individual program can be.

Q: In your review of Amundson's book (Wagner 2006), you stress the problem of historicity.

R: One of the big ironies of the intellectual history of evolutionary biology is that evolutionary biology gained respectability as a completely ahistorical science. From the 21st century perspective

that's rather puzzling. I can make a story of why that is the case, although I don't know how much that reflects historical reality. But it is at least a fact that there was a very strong anti-historical stance in the classical population genetics literature. That is partly methodological, partly the physicalist idea of science, i.e., trying to be as similar to the structure of physics as possible, with the Fisherian maximization principles and so on. And in part, it was because the way of inferring past events was not firmly established, it was not very respectable at the time, with phylogenetic methods slowly forming. It only really happened in the late 20th century with cladistics and phylogenetic taxonomy; and with new kinds of data like molecular sequences; the discovery of conserved genetic elements, which in the past and with no data at hand at the time was assumed to be nonexistent. I think a lot of these things changed the landscape for the acceptability of the historical perspective.

I think one of the deepest things we can understand about biology and life is its fundamental historicity, which came into focus since devo-evo came to life, with conserved genes and also the understanding of complex dynamics, bifurcations, and so on ... historicity even in the small physical world of snowflakes. I think it's an important, perhaps sometimes underestimated, paradigm shift in the way people think about nature: from an ahistorical process view to one that is mostly dominated by general laws of nature.

Q: Another issue you refer to is the tension between generalities and differences. This is a topic you refer to in your work with Stopper (Stopper & Wagner 2005), where you stress what you call the “potentially obscuring assumption of universality” of limb developmental mechanisms.

R: This also relates to the historicity perspective. I think population geneticists would not necessarily have this point of view because they have these general principles of selection, drift, and mutation and that's essentially the world they live in. Variation plays a role, but it's variation between individuals, not between clades or species. This is [Reeve and Sherman's \(1993\)](#) metaphor of the “ancestors reaching out of their tombs to clutch the throats of the descendants” problem.

Q: In your paper with Larsson on how to test hypotheses in devo-evo (Larsson & Wagner 2012), you warn of the risk of devo-evo telling just-so stories, like adaptationism.

R: That's one of those papers that only philosophers read. It was not written in a way that would be appealing to biologists [...]

Certainly, the easier thing to do is to tell just-so stories. My optimism that this doesn't have to be the end of the story comes from the fact that we're making much progress in what you loosely can call synthetic biology, our ability to manipulate and reprogram cells and organisms. This has of course implications for application in biomedicine, engineering, and so on. But what is interesting for me is that it actually harbours the possibility of doing evolutionary synthetic biology, where you take an

outgroup species that doesn't have a derived character, study the ingroup and make a model of how this evolutionary change may have happened. Then go to an organism without the derived feature, and synthesize the derived feature in it. That would be the ultimate way of rigorously testing the stories that we can deduce from comparative developmental work.

I'm sure I will fail in this the same way I failed in simulating the evolution of evolvability, but for instance, we could try to understand how the decidual stromal cell evolved in a new cell type in eutherian mammals, then take the homologous cell type in the opossum and introduce certain changes to have the first steps towards a cell that behaves like the decidual cell. That would be the ideal realization of that field. It's sort of analogous to what's going on in organic chemistry: you have the analytical part, isolating a molecule, you try to figure out what it looks like by breaking it into different ways, look at what fragments come out, and then build a model of how the thing hangs together. But that's only a theory. You can only say you've proven that's the structure of the molecule if you actually synthesize the molecule from smaller ones. I think the same way of thinking applies to evolutionary biology. There are already fields where that's possible. In particular protein evolution, where you can do sequence comparisons, calculate the most likely ancestral amino acid sequence, synthesize this peptide in the lab, and study it. And then actually change certain amino acids to recreate the evolutionary transformation of, let's say, a glucocorticoid receptor into another receptor. That's already successful at that level, although it's not easy. We've also done some degree of that kind of work where we have been identifying amino acid substitutions that give a transcription factor a new regulatory capability. That's possible there because we know how to reconstruct amino acid sequences and we have the technology to make basically any protein that we want in vitro. So once we have it we can study it either in vitro or by introducing it into a cell and see how it behaves there. I think the kind of work Payne is doing, simulating synthetic networks, can lead to reconstructing what the gene regulatory network of the ancestor may have looked like, and actually making it synthetically, studying it, and changing it to see if our ideas about its transformation were right or not. Once we are at that point, the just-so stories will be much fewer.

Q: You have shown an interest in the influence of computer science in evolutionary biology (Wagner 1995). What role did computational science play in your understanding of modularity and evolvability?

R: It played essentially the same role as the engineering approach; it was just a reaffirmation of this basic idea. It was also a field that developed another approach to the problem of evolvability related to representations. On the other hand, it also provided an avenue to explore ideas with computational models that can be more complex than the mathematical models that I usually work with. With Calabretta, we found ways in which a modular architecture could evolve (Calabretta et al. 2000). It

was both a technical advantage and a conceptual one, where the notion of representation as a factor in the variational properties and therefore evolvability of the systems was developed.

Q: How was your collaboration with Lee Altenberg?

R: This collaboration was largely limited to the [Wagner and Altenberg 1996] paper. He did a lot of work to actually formally define it in a way that is quite attractive to me, even if none of my friends agree with that idea and not many people seem to know about it. His definition is an analogy of heritability. The idea of heritability is that you have it if the parents that deviate from the mean have a likelihood of producing offspring that deviate from the mean in the same way. Altenberg's idea was that evolvability can be defined by the probability that genotypes that are selectively advantageous have the propensity to produce further improved genotypes by mutation so that there's a positive statistical relationship between past and future evolvability in terms of the likelihood of advantageous mutations. This is a measure that could supplement Hansen and Houle's [2008] use of standing genetic variation and would be a property to apply to the supply of new mutations to the population, to the next level of evolvability that depends on new genetic variation.

Q: How did you become interested in the neutral networks approach? How did your collaboration with Peter Stadler start?

R: The neutral networks idea originated in theoretical chemistry with Schuster, rather than in computer science. Schuster, Fontana, and others developed the idea of configuration spaces and neutral networks, as well as their implications for evolvability, although they didn't call it that way.

The collaboration with Stadler was initiated through some empirical work that we were doing on the evolution of Hox clusters and developmental control genes, comparing sequences among different species and seeing how they evolved. So it was a relatively applied work of data analysis originally. The more interesting conceptual work came later when we developed the idea of configuration spaces as ways of talking about the landscape of evolutionary possibilities, which was first articulated in [Stadler et al. 2001]. The idea is to generalize the notion of topology to apply to these configuration spaces, which in many ways are more primitive than the spaces that we usually think of. One of the limitations of evolutionary genetics, and particularly quantitative genetics, is that it always assumes that the range of possibilities can be arranged in an Euclidean, 3D space. That is a very strong topological class of spaces, while the question is whether we can use tools from the mathematics of topology, to characterize the configuration space of, let's say, RNA secondary structure, and other phenotype spaces that are not defined in an Euclidean space.

That led us to the idea that we can develop a framework that's flexible enough to allow talking about innovation. In the quantitative genetics context, all the traits that you measure on an organism have to

be present in all organisms that you compare. So you can only model modifications of existing traits: how they get bigger, smaller, or are correlated, for example. But situations where new traits appear, and therefore the basis for the description of the organism changes, are intrinsically impossible to implement. In a paper that we published a few years later [Wagner & Stadler 2003], we actually developed a mathematical and conceptual framework where we say that characters are the dimensions of the phenotype space that you can locally define this dimensionality. You assume that you consider all the possibilities, and then see in how many directions the variation takes place. Then, innovations happen when you move from one part of the configuration space to another one where the number of local dimensions is different. To my knowledge, that would be the first mathematically rigorous framework where true innovation can actually be talked about. There are difficulties in applying this, but on an in-principle basis, we give directions on where to go to make the mathematical language of evolutionary theory flexible enough to incorporate events of true innovation. [...] You need a special combination of talents and interests: both being strongly conceptually-oriented, and also strong in mathematics, and among biologists you don't find this too often. It's somewhat of a pity that that line of research didn't continue.

Q: You've shown an interest in navigating complex adaptive landscapes [Wagner & Stadler 1999, Stadler et al 2000]. Some people are reluctant to this approach precisely because the adaptive dimension is not always included.

R: But it can be seamlessly integrated. The configuration space is a set of states that are connected by the possible mutational effects of how you can turn one into the other. This space plays the same role as the Euclidean space in quantitative genetics, to which you can attach a fitness value to each of the nodes. Then you have adaptive dynamics in there immediately incorporated, so there's no barrier to integrating these two perspectives. I think the stronger claim about these spaces being anti-adaptationist is that the rate of adaptive evolution is controlled by the topological features of the configuration space. And whether a phenotype is in the position of likely mutating into an alternative phenotype and getting selected for or against depends on the random localization of genotypes along the neutral network. That is not controlled, by definition, by natural selection; otherwise, it wouldn't be neutral. I think the anti-adaptationist consequence is that there are features in the organism that have a higher control over the outcome of evolution than natural selection. It is not that the framework itself cannot integrate into the idea of fitness differences affecting gene or genotype frequencies. Rather, it's the fact that in those cases that can be represented in the configuration space, in neutral network models, the explanatory power of natural selection is much less than it is when you assume a Euclidean space of all possibilities and smooth transitions [...]

Q: In your work, you cite philosophy papers from very early on. What led you to be interested in philosophy? How did it influence your work?

R: [...] My predisposition to go in that direction was already in the motivation that led me to study biology rather than continue as a chemist, namely the conceptual openness and the not-completely-formed nature of biology. There are conceptual issues in other sciences as well, but at the micro level of physics and chemistry the conceptual landscape is more or less fixed. Also, I am a product of my academic background, and at the University of Vienna philosophy is everywhere. There are sciences seminars that are essentially philosophical, and of course we had philosophical topics in the seminars with my advisor. Even in the rules for earning a PhD you had to have two main exams in your main field (in my case zoology), two exams in philosophy, and one exam in the minor (mathematical logic in my case). In a way, in terms of the number of final exams, philosophy was treated on equal footing with the main area of study.

In a more general sense, these connections are always necessary in times when the conceptual inventory of a science is changing. You can do excellent science in an area where the conceptual issues have been settled in the past: you don't need to reach back to Aristotle in order to synthesize a molecule, because it's reasonably clear what you're doing. That is not the case in wide areas of biology: we still discuss what a gene is, what we mean by that; the species concept we reasonably know what it is but still have discussions about it; we're reopening the homology discussion with all the empirical evidence that come from various areas; the emphasis on cell types and their origination raises its own conceptual questions, that in my opinion are similar to the homology questions. Those corners of science are always intellectually more exciting, and thereby also prone to be influenced by, relevant to, and receptive to philosophical reflection.

Q: In the early 2000s you wrote a series of papers on developmental evolution (Wagner 2000b, 2001, Wagner & Larsson 2003). How would you define it? How does it relate to other fields of evo-devo and why hasn't this distinction been retained in evolutionary biology?

R: The keyword is devo-evo versus evo-devo. I think it's only so confusing because we use these short "evo" and "devo" terms. I think it's clearer if you say "developmental evolutionary biology" or "evolutionary developmental biology", because it shows the emphasis. Developmental evolutionary biology (devo-evo) is a branch of evolutionary biology that aims to understand the processes and patterns of evolutionary change with the tools and the insights from developmental biology, analogous to how molecular evolutionary biology is the branch of evolutionary biology that uses the tools and insights from molecular genetics. I think there is a difference in scientific aim, where devo-evo is a branch of evolutionary biology that wants to understand evolution from the perspective of development, while the majority of work in evolutionary developmental biology is a branch of developmental biology that tries to understand how development is changing in evolution rather than development as a tool to understand the evolutionary change. Of course they overlap and learn from each other, but I think as a discipline they're fundamentally different.

The reason why evo-devo is dominant is because the empirical discipline grew out of developmental biology and is dominated by it, so the most influential people, like Sean Carroll, Cliff Tabin, Rudi Raff, they all come from developmental biology. Their interest in evolution, or even their understanding of problems in it, is distant for them. The way they approach it is the more productive and stronger research program, and naturally that dominates the field. It's OK, that's how it is. I think in devo-evo we're suffering from a lack of understanding of how specifically developmental insights can inform evolutionary thinking and how these inferences can be tested. We discussed already that once we have an evolutionary synthetic biology that will change, because we will specifically be able to rigorously test scenarios that explain evolutionary transformations. Of course, in some ways this is a rhetorical game that we're playing, where we're accusing each other, which in itself is fun but shouldn't be taken too seriously.

Q: How does your approach contrast with ahistorical approaches in evo-devo?

R: I think the role of historicity, or lack of that role in some branches of evolutionary developmental biology is best illustrated with the cis-regulatory paradigm controversy. The cis regulatory paradigm, which was dominant and still is very broadly defended, is exactly a way of thinking about the evolution of gene regulation, which is the mechanistic side of the evolution of development. I compare it to a "Lego" approach, where everything can be combined with everything else, because all you have to know is to change the cis regulatory elements, and you can actually recombine and do anything you want. Our work on transcription factor evolution, and that of other people as well, shows that transcription factors, which interact with cis regulatory elements, are not in every case exchangeable between species. They require specific regulatory capabilities that are specific to a particular tissue type, species or group of species. That is one of the places where true historicity is introduced, because it leads to the non-replaceability of certain parts of the gene-regulatory network machinery.

I'm not denying that large part of gene regulatory evolution is cis regulatory, that's not the question. But to claim that there's 'nothing else but it' isn't right either. This is always the problem, particularly in biology: when people make statements about "nothing else but" whatever you want to refer to, that usually leads to overgeneralizations. I think that in macroevolution and the evolution of body plans, the way historicity enters the picture is when the kind of evolutionary change that's happening leads to non-replaceability or functional non-equivalence of parts. I think there's a very strong cognitive bias to like scientific models that suggest a strong ability to manipulate stuff, in an engineering way; there's a mental bias that makes these models attractive to scientists and the general public. But I think it's an insidious bias, because you underestimate the aspects of evolved historical uniqueness.

There are ethical consequences as well to reflect on, since this bias tends to minimize the dignity and uniqueness of individuals, kinds of organisms, species and so on. The most striking articulation of this attitude is in one of the books of Eric Davidson, who I otherwise love to death, but we have this

philosophical disagreement. In one Introduction he writes that cis-regulatory elements are the core of what a species is because it determines the dynamic of the developmental process, so when a species goes extinct what's really important to be mourned is the loss of all the cis-regulatory elements that make up the nature of the species. So basically a species becomes reduced to a collection of cis-regulatory elements, which I find dangerously reductionist in the way of thinking about organisms in general. The annoying thing is not so much that people think in this way, but rather that these ethical consequences are based on partial and incomplete science. It is not true that what leads to this way of thinking is the best science, but it's just the science that people like to hear.

Q: In the mid-1990s, you started arguing that explicit genetic models are necessary for understanding pleiotropy (Baatz & Wagner 1997)

R: I think it was a realization that very unstructured quantitative genetic models that we had worked on in the past were just incapable of reflecting what's going on in the evolution of modules.

Why is quantitative genetics so seductive? Because it's very good in one particular task, namely predicting the amount of change of the mean value, which is almost independent of any detail, and all that is needed to know is selection strength and heritability. There was already a paper by [Turelli & Barton](#) in part answering to Lande's way of modeling evolution. They showed that if we not only want to know what happens to the mean value but also to the variances and covariances under selection, executing a mathematical model for that would require one to know incredible detail about the distribution of allelic effects at each locus that is affecting this character. In one respect, if you're interested in the mean, you have basically no difficulty or very little, you'll need an aggregate measure of heritability. But as soon as you go to a second order feature like the variance, then all hell breaks loose. All the ability to aggregate and simplify and have a macroscopic thermodynamics-like theory of what's going on is just completely impossible. Only under extremely simplifying assumptions can you see anything.

In my opinion, that's where the point or the ideology of Lande's approach breaks down. His theories about how genetic variances and covariances change or have equilibrium under certain conditions are highly questionable, and if you do realistic models you see there's no way of simplifying anything. It really all hell breaks loose. This leads to disillusionment with models that hope to develop macroscopic theories of evolutionary change and tell us that details matter. Detail matters because of historicity and because everything that matters depends on detail. There's no escape from it, and that's a very strong mathematical result that we cannot deny.

Once you realize that that's the case, then the only way is to find the smallest number of details that matter, and totally change your perspective from one where you hope to get large-scale, broad

generalizations, to one where you take details seriously, because not only the Devil but also God and the angels live in them: they all live in detail when it comes to life.

Q: However, you haven't abandoned your search for generality, as seen in your work on homology.

R: I think there are different kinds of generalizations. Generalizations that are realistic to be made on biological evolution and organisms in general are, at a large scale, patterns where there are phases of stasis and innovations, a little bit similar to paradigm shifts and normal science. I think the kind of generalization that I'm aiming for is different from the generalizations I was hoping for in population genetics theory, because the generalizations that I'm attracted to right now is the idea that everything relevant in biology is essentially a historical individual. And the best we can hope for is to identify those individuals that have medium to long-scale existence, and which are the actual players in whatever detail is going on in addition. It is a very history-centered perspective, where the identification of the players in the historical process is the primary objective, such as homologues, cell types, genes, body plans, etc. Those are contingently originating, but then forming or constraining further history. So there's a dialectic between radical innovation and conservation after a phase of revolution or innovation. There's analogy also with politics, where there are phases of relatively normal historical non-change, or slow change within the political system, and then phases of radical change of the rules under which political life unfolds. I think there's an analogy in biology, not by coincidence, because human life and social life are an extension of biology and I don't think there's any fundamental difference in the nature of the process.

For me, innovations in the most general sense, are evolutionary events that changed the rules of adaptive evolution. The normal mode of evolutionary change, adapting to your local environment, all that is most of the time happening with the same type of players and the same type of spaces of possibilities, but then there are sometimes transformative events where the rules and the players change fundamentally. Those are the major transitions, but also other minor transitions that lead to different forms of life that play the evolutionary game of adaptation in different ways.

Q: What's your view on the "macroevolutionary lag"?

R: I think that comes from the misunderstanding that the innovation itself is the origin of a particular trait, property or body part. Real innovation is happening when these novel traits that can actually exist longer get integrated into the network of interdependent and autocatalytic ecological and even social change. It's just never the trait itself that is a novelty at the developmental level, but at the evolutionary level, when it finds the right conditions in which it can play a new role.

For instance, a simple example is that there is an intriguing correlation between genome duplications and adaptive radiations. On the one hand there's a gap between genome duplication that comes earlier, and radiations that come later. But there's also the other paradox: there are many genome duplications that don't lead to anything. *Xenopus* frogs have genome duplications all the time, and they don't do anything interesting. The way of understanding this is that the potential of organismal change is intrinsic, for instance in the duplication of the genome, while the opportunity that presents itself from the ecological side needs to meet the former. Then you find the real transformative period in evolution.

Q: In your edited book on modularity (Schlosser & Wagner 2004), the attempt was precisely to combine developmental and evolutionary approaches. What's your current view on such an integration?

R: In one way, the idea of modularity also underlies my ideas about cell types, homologs, body parts and so on. Even though surprisingly I don't use that language often enough. I gave up on the modularity field as a framing of a research program at the point when I failed to reliably model the origin of modularity. It turned out to be not entirely trivial to come up with models that naturally lead to modularity, particularly if you use quantitative genetics models. Other people have been successful, but always in the case of highly contrived modules, like Kashtan and Uri Alon, from the Weizmann Institute of Science. They make models that are very artificial, Boolean networks models that are more inspired by computer science than by any biological realism.

Thinking about modules is a way to sort out thoughts about organisms, and how they are put together is still an important perspective. As an evolutionary problem I failed to explain their origin. From my work, I think the only times when I was successful was with Calabretta [see Calabretta et al. 2000; Wagner et al. 2005], but that didn't lead to a general theory establishing the conditions under which a module arises. Maybe it turns out that it was a poorly articulated question. That might be the case, it may have been too abstract to ask for the conditions for the evolution of modularity with such a generality. I don't know, but it didn't seem to be a very productive research program to ask this question in the modeling, theoretical way.

Q: How did a population geneticist like you become interested in homology?

R: That is one of the natural entry points into the way of thinking where you want to reconstitute scientific talk about the structure of the organism. Multicellular organisms, but also some unicell organisms, display their complexity by the heterogeneity of their parts. Those are the objects that we have captured and described in comparative anatomy and that led to the notion of homology, namely the same or corresponding body parts in different organisms. That led to the discovery that organisms are evolutionary related to each other, and we come to that conclusion because they share so many features. So in that respect it's a natural question to ask.

But at the same time, it was something that had a minimal scientific reputation [...] I felt like we cannot go on in evolutionary organismal biology without reconstructing that concept in a way that can productively interact with and learn from population genetics, developmental biology, and generally modern biology. Basically, it's about rewriting homology for the mechanistic phase in the history of biology. You have to rescue what phenomenology and knowledge is captured by that concept so that it can be part of a modern understanding of life. [...]

The question is whether homologies are residues of history, or whether they play a more important theoretical role in evolutionary thinking. George Williams, as an influential population thinker, more or less defined homology as the existence of a mere residue of historical change that is otherwise impervious to what was in the past. Under that view, history is only something that's stochastic, a random residue, rather than something that also shapes our understanding of how evolution moves forward.

Q: In your 1989 paper on the biological homology concept, you overview different ways to individuate homological relationships (Wagner 1989a). Were you in touch with other people working on homology?

R: Mostly, we knew each other from the literature, particularly [Leigh] Van Valen, but I was aware of Louise Roth, we personally interacted at the time. I think, in part coming from morphologists and from developmental biologists, the homology question sort of bubbled up naturally. The fact that this work had the resonance it had is because it was introduced at the right time in the history of biology. That's always the case, like in major evolutionary innovations: new ideas, just like new characters, only have an impact if they find themselves in the right historical context.

Q: Since then one of your main puzzles has been the stability of form as compared to the variability of development. In your work with Bernhard Misof (Wagner & Misof 1993), you distinguish between generative and morphostatic constraints. Is it the same type of distinction that you later introduce between kinds of mechanisms contributing to character identity?

R: That's an interesting bifurcation, actually. In the earlier attempts, I was more concerned with the observation that many homologues have conserved features and are therefore recognizable as individuated. Later on, and I think this came together in the 2007 *Nature* review [Wagner 2007] and made enough sense to write the book [Wagner 2014], I realized that the real problem was not how a homologue looks but how it distinguishes itself from other parts of the body. I understood that that was the intellectually deeper, the more critical problem to solve at this 2006-2007 time. This is analogous to the realization in the 20th century that a species is not what it is because of how it looks and what it does, but because it is an independent line of evolutionary change. I think that this connection only occurred to me in the mid 2000s, maybe even influenced to some degree by the

[Ghiselin](#) paper in a 2004 symposium in Jena on homologues as historical individuals. That was probably an important realization, and once you phrase it that way, you have a clearer agenda of what mechanistically you have to explain.

Q: But you already formulated it that way in your character book ([Wagner 2000a](#)).

R: That is possible because you never remember what you said before. That's probably how the mind works. It's the same thing as with those themes that were already in the 1981 Dahlem conference: many of the things that we now are very excited about were already articulated back then and nothing happened for decades before you return to it without knowing why or how. But also, I have a bad memory. I don't remember that well.

Q: You recently mentioned that you no longer were thinking in terms of “character identity networks” ([Wagner 2007](#)), but more generally in terms of character identity mechanisms. Can you expand on that?

R: At the time when I wrote [[Wagner 2007](#)], which inspired the [[2014](#)] book, the dominant way of thinking about gene regulation was in terms of gene regulatory networks. The character identity network was a parallel idea to the one by Hobert, Eric Davidson and others ... We more or less formulated a very similar idea based on completely independent research programs. That was encouraging, because when multiple people arrive at the same conclusion independently it's more likely to be meaningful.

There were maybe two things that led me to alternative ways of thinking about this. One has to do with the case of the evolution of the decidual cell that we work on. If the character identity network idea was really applicable, you would expect functional genomic tools to be able to identify the network by measuring the expression of all the genes and how gene expression changes under perturbations, and refining cis-regulatory elements and so on. With all that information we should be able to build a good model of all gene regulatory interactions that go on in a cell. If that's possible and if you're able to isolate them. That turned out to be extremely difficult. That's an empirical outcome.

The other thing in which my notion of ChINs differed from other similar proposals was that I already at that time took into account that many gene products of these supposed core regulatory networks don't act alone, physically. The transcription factor proteins physically interact and produce a complex that has a certain regulatory capability, able to regulate the expression of certain genes and not others. The actual physical agent that determines the expression of genes in cell types is not a combination of independent transcription factors, but rather a novel emergent molecular entity that comes from integrating all of these things together into one blob that is specifically modified and then does the

regulation. So the different transcription factors from the core network don't act independently on the gene regulatory landscape.

That also resonated with the fact that we have transcription factor protein changes in the trans regulatory capability that we could map to the phase in evolution when this new cell type arose. A lot of evidence was actually pushing us towards looking at the role of changes in transcription factor proteins and their role in emergent units of gene regulatory agents. So that leads to this idea that it's not a core regulatory network but a core regulatory complex that is specific to each cell type, and has a trans regulatory landscape that is specific for a particular cell type, leading to the cell type specific expression of effector genes.

On the one hand, I think that these core network ideas came from an experimental tradition where only a few genes could be interrogated, and then it looked like there were nicely separated networks. But if you a priori go into the system and look at everything, it's not that obvious that you can find these supposedly neatly separated core-regulatory sub-networks. They may exist in other systems, but they don't in our cells as far as I can tell, and I'm not sure about whether we would identify the same core networks if we look at a sea urchin with enough resolution we will identify the same kernels as Davidson did.

So that made me aware that maybe what is the most plausible intellectual figure that you could put in that place to do something [to explain cell type identity] needs to be loosened, and all that we can say is that there has to be some mechanism that does "X". You can say that it's instantiated in a kernel or a core regulatory network, and another possibility might be a protein complex with some cell type-specific functionality. And there might be things going on with large non-coding RNAs and their interactions with proteins, for example. We cannot predict what's possible in this regard. I think if we introduce a concept we shouldn't tie it too tightly to one particular way of thinking of how things work. It's always a partial, and in many ways wrong, sort of temporary valid perspective. Therefore it's more productive to tie the notion of character identity to the hypothesis that there has to be a mechanism that fulfills a particular functional role, rather than to tie yourself to a particular possible realization of that. At the time there were not many alternatives, but now that I've learned more molecular biology I think it's pretty obvious that we should be more open in that respect.

Q: You have worked on the conflict between typological and populational thinking. It seems like it's still hard to defend a non-idealistic notion of type that plays a role in evolutionary theory. How do you understand an evolving type and how does that relate to evolvability?

R: Of course, I talk about typology or typological thinking in a sort of different way than traditionally was meant to be. I think in my book I talk about variational typology, which is exactly the kind of synthesis of the realization that evolutionary change requires variation but at the same time variation is

not uniformly distributed all over the organismal traits. What I call variational typology just realizes that some configurations, some traits, some parts of the body plan, are fairly fixed after a certain point in phylogenetic history. That's just an empirical fact that needs to be accommodated in evolutionary theory. It accommodates what was the empirical basis for typological thinking to begin with. I think extreme positions about everything being variable are not well founded on empirical fact. The fact that some body parts are conserved, for reasons that we can broadly understand, does not entail anti-evolutionary commitments because it makes no statements about the evolvability of other parts of the body. If those other parts are less constrained they are the subject of natural selection, which causes changes on them. I think this polarity is just silly.

Q: You have worked on classical case-studies for illustrating this point, such as digit evolution or the fin-limb transition, but you have recently moved towards the study of homological processes or functions, such as menstruation, female orgasm, or pregnancy. Has the study of processes, as opposed to parts, influenced your views on homology?

R: I think it's still early to say for me. The reason that I got into the evolution of female reproduction was a chain of coincidences that had no deep conceptual meaning in itself. It was driven by opportunity with short sequences of decisions. We wanted to work in a particular gene because it's involved in fin and limb development, and discovered that this gene evolves fast in the mammalian lineage, and people already knew that this same gene in mice is necessary for the maintenance of pregnancy. That's, of course, a novel mode of reproduction. So we had two observations. The one is that it's a gene that's important for reproduction and that pregnancy is a novelty. The other is that we have a signal of change in the genes and we wanted to see what's the connection. We could eventually show that the transcription factor protein evolution involved changes that were necessary for the function of this protein in decidualization, so it has to do with the cell type that accommodates the placenta and the foetus in the uterus. That led to a lot of work for trying to understand biochemically what's behind this transcription factor protein evolution, which on the side solved the problem of why it's not the case that transcription factor proteins cannot evolve, why the cis paradigm was wrong. Then we worked on proteins in female reproductive cell types, and realized that the cell type is also new. So the cell type itself became interesting, but of course it evolved because it fulfills a function, and that led to the broader question of how that relates to the evolution of pregnancy in general. So that snowballed into a full research program of the evolution of female reproduction in mammals, with a parallel strain in trying to understand the origin of a new cell type.

It's interesting because it leads to an area of biology that's intrinsically fascinating because it is interactive and interdependent: there are functional and physiological relationships between two individuals, if you want, that partially have different genomes. So it's really a chance to learn about a part of biology that is extremely interesting, important and that has made relatively little conceptual

progress over the last 30 years. So it's another field where a lot of exciting questions can be asked in a way that nobody has asked before. And there's a feedback cycle where you get attention and get rewarded for doing that, so it commits you even more to this work that I really like.

Maybe the most interesting conceptual impact of this is that I was fairly committed to only talk about homology and the origin of structural characters because of my interest in details that I mentioned before, but that naturally led me to think about not only homology of structure but also homology of processes or functional performances. That extended my thinking, first in a way that I didn't even realize. The work with Pavlicev in the evolution of female orgasm [Pavlicev & Wagner 2016, 2019; Wagner & Pavlicev 2017] just used homology thinking without even realizing that I was doing something completely different. It was Alan Love who pointed out at a visit of mine in Minnesota that I was talking about the homology of a process, or function. That is interesting, when you realize that a conceptual approach may be even more useful than you thought before because it naturally led to applications you never intended to engage in [...] I don't think I'm done with that, I can't give you a full account about it, but this move towards process homology is probably the best example.

Q: This is also the first work that has linked the evolution of development to the evolution of reproduction.

R: And that is surprising. I haven't studied it systematically, but I think it actually reflects the fact that there was a huge progress in the 1950-60s up to the 1970s in reproductive biology, both in the clinical as well as in the comparative ground, but then all that fell away and there was a fairly sterile field where concepts from the 1950s kept around but nothing new was happening. An example is that everyone in reproductive immunology follows the ideas of Medawar, and I say it without any disrespect. Some clinicians start to question this way of thinking about the fetal-maternal immunological relationship. Good friends of mine who are clinical scientists and practitioners tell me that it leads to clinical malpractice, because the ideas lead to therapeutic interventions that are not good neither for the woman nor for the foetus. So it's a really exciting area where devo-evo thinking hasn't had an impact, maybe with the exception of Marty Cohn from Florida, who mostly looks at male external genitalia under a devo-evo perspective. But from the female side, or in particular the non-placental part of the story, there was basically nothing. It's one of the areas where I like to be, because a lot of new thinking and new discoveries are possible, particularly also where evolutionary thinking can have a major impact because it hasn't been used to try to systematize the knowledge in the field. [...]

Another thing that I learned from engaging with the problem of the origin and evolution of pregnancy is an appreciation of how difficult some transitions that from a functional point of view should be obviously advantageous, are from a mechanistic point of view. I started to appreciate more the role of the homeostatic tendencies of the organism, and thereby opposing change, has to be part of the

thinking about the possibility of evolutionary change. If the change is radical enough, it is only possible if not only this alternative character state can be realized, but it has to happen in a context in which the intervening forces of homeostasis of the organism are overcome in a way that is not damaging the organism. For example, our work on inflammation suggests that the form of deep implantation that is so typical for eutherians was particularly difficult evolutionarily because it implies the development of a wound in the maternal tissue that any tissue would counteract by wound healing inflammation and so on, which would be incompatible with the continuation of pregnancy. So it's not enough to evolve the capability of the foetus to invade and establish a deep connection with the maternal physiology, but it is also necessary that the mother evolves to tolerate at certain points, certain parts of the body, the maintenance of an open wound. At a mechanistic level, that means that the fact that the organism is intrinsically homeostatic always makes the realization of a radical change complex, because it has to overcome interdependencies that are not obvious if you only look at the end product and its functional fitness level. The move into this area, knowing more about pregnancy and physiology in general, has led me to an appreciation of the role that organismal homeostasis plays in opposing evolutionary change. If you just look from a population genetics point of view that would never occur to you.

Q: What are your current views on the evolution of evolvability?

R: If anything, I've become more agnostic as time goes on. Now I think that what we learned is how difficult it is to distinguish between scenarios [selected or as a trade-off]. It is hard enough to prove that something is an adaptation when it's a single trait, like pigmentation. Evolvability is a second-order property, because it's a variational property, and I think it will be even more difficult. It really is an open question.

My whole thinking started out with the idea that evolvability is an adaptive consequence, an adaptive answer to the curse of dimensionality. You have to structure your variational properties or tendencies appropriately so the chances of adaptive evolution increase. I think it's a really ingenious general idea that Riedl had, but whether that's happening ever or whether it can happen in principle is still a totally open question. So far, it led to many positive developments in evolutionary biology. An emphasis on the evolution of variational properties, like robustness, is all positive because it opens the horizon of evolutionary research to new questions. And in the end it's probably not important whether the initial idea was correct or not, because conceptual developments are justified, or have fulfilled their promise, if they lead to productive research programs. Whether these research programs deliver what we thought they would is a secondary question.

I like an analogy with philosophy of science. Carnap had the idea that maybe we can understand the discovery of natural laws in an inductive way by developing a calculus of subjective probability. My understanding is that that project failed, but nevertheless enabled developments in decision theory and

economic theory that are productive in themselves. That may not have happened without the original idea of Carnap of trying to have a calculus of inductive reasoning. Ultimately, this project failed in its original intent, but that's irrelevant because it had other positive consequences. It could be the same with evolvability, or at least the strand of evolvability thinking that I'm part of, coming from this grand idea where the evolution of evolvability would explain everything. If that fails, it would have still been worthwhile, because along the way we learned a lot of stuff and we created areas of biological research that might not have happened at that time without it. I think I'm rather stoic in that respect.

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